

A Real Time FPGA-Based Implementation for Detection and Sorting of Bio-signals

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Abstract Extract and analyse relevant information from bio-signal recordings are complex tasks where Action Potential Detection and Sorting processes take place, yet if these are performed in real-time. In this regard, the present paper introduces real-time FPGA-based architectures for detection and sorting of biosignals, in particular Macaque and human pancreatic signals. Action Potential Detection is performed by using an adaptive threshold. Also, during this process we have identified six different Action Potential shapes from the signals, which have been used to classify the Action Potentials. Our implementation runs at a frequency of 100 MHz with a low resource consumption for both architectures and Action Potentials can be also observed in real-time during a simulation in an OLED display.

Keywords FPGA · Bio-signals · VHDL · Sorting · Action

1 Introduction

The electro-physiology is the study of the electrical properties of biological cells and tissues that measure and analyse the changes of voltages or electric currents such as the Action Potentials (APs), which are spontaneous electrical activities collected through electrodes. This electrical activity can come from individual neurons or interactions among them. In this regard, multi-cell recording is a commonly used technique to extract this electrical information from cell-cultures and tissue slices

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in order to find treatments for human diseases and disorders. In the particular case of endocrine cells [12], this information is not the only one recorded during the process, also we can find noise, Local Field Potentials (LFP) [8,2,3,10], and Slow Waves Potentials (SWP). Frequently, LFP are in the low-frequency band of (1-100 Hz) [11]. They represent the sum of current sources reflecting the synaptic activity of tens or thousands or nearby neurons. Moreover, Slow Waves Potentials in endocrine cells have a band frequency below than 1 Hz [14]. The neural firing rate activity where Action Potentials are observed, is commonly found in the band of 100-10 000 Hz [11]. To automatically handle different frequency bands and to deal with the problems associated to bio-signals recording experiments, adaptive thresholds have been successfully used [14].

Besides, algorithms for Action Potential sorting are composed of three parts, detection, feature extraction and clustering [17,4]. In addition, there exist mathematical methods to compute thresholds during AP detection [13]. Traditional methods such as NEO [9,7,19], are used to detect Action Potentials in hardware, however this technique reduces its accuracy when multiple frequency components and noise are present, thus several false detections could take place [1,18]. Other methods such as wavelet detectors require excessive hardware resources [6,18].

This work aims to propose a novel method for detection and sorting of biosignals and its implementation in hardware. Here, we improved the adaptive threshold parameters for computing an appropriate threshold in order to successfully detect Action Potentials in biosignals recordings. So, we tested the adaptive threshold of [5], which does not need many resources and its implementation in hardware is straightforward. In addition, this adaptive threshold is not sensible to Action Potentials when appropriate parameters are selected.

Our strategy is to use this adaptive threshold with the generation of a Mean Action Potential shape to be correlated with the Action Potentials detected, in that way, we use the technique of match filtering using the correlation to generate the autocorrelation signal between those shapes. Afterwards, when Action Potentials and Mean Action Potential shape match, a correlation pattern is generated. Therefore, we detected this pattern to classify each Action Potential detection among six possible groups, depending on its correlation pattern detected. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time where correlation patterns are detected by adaptive thresholds.

2 Materials and Methods

In this section, we describe the methods and materials used in this research. Methods are graphically represented in Figure 1, where raw signals correspond to macaque monkey signals recorded *in vivo* with a 40 KHz sampling frequency and human pancreatic signals with a 10 KHz sampling frequency. These signals are then pre-processed using an IIR Band-pass filter to accentuate Action Potentials and remove Local Field Potentials and Slow Waves into the recordings. The Action Potential Detection block is implemented using an adaptive threshold, which computes a threshold above the background noise of the bio-signal in real-time and saves the maximum value of the Action Potentials when these are above such threshold. In the next block, we use an IIR low-pass filter to compute a shape template from all Action Potentials detected throughout the whole signal.

Fig. 1: General block diagram of the proposal

Next, a correlation is applied in the Mean Action Potential block to each new sample read and processed by the band-pass filter (preprocessing block). Finally, in the correlation block, six different patterns are detected and classified with the maximum sample number of the Action Potential shape that was stored.

All these blocks are now described in detail.

2.1 Raw data

As was aforementioned, two bio-signals were used in this work to validate the performance of our hardware implementation with real data, on one hand a macaque monkey signal sampled at 40 KHz and on the other hand a human pancreatic signal at 10 KHz. The signals were then stored in a SD card and they are directly read by the FPGA. Access to the SD card is similar to a RAM memory and data can be 8, 16, 32 and 64 bits wide. In our case, we used a 16-bit data word size.

2.2 Bio-signal preprocessing

The bio-signal preprocessing basically consists of a filtering stage, where band-pass filters are designed to deal with the noise involved in the macaque monkey and the pancreatic signals aforementioned. The band-pass filters have been designed from low-pass and high-pass filters, where the latter is designed by using spectral inversion. For the low-pass filter, an Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) is used due that it has a faster and long impulse response. From the general form of the IIR filter equation [16], our low-pass filter for both bio-signals reads:

$$y[n] = 0.75 y[n-1] + 0.125 x[n] + 0.125 x[n-1] \quad (1)$$

For a digital implementation (e.g. FPGA) the last equation can be rewritten as follows:

$$y[n] = y[n-1] - \frac{y[n-1]}{4} + \frac{x[n]}{8} + \frac{x[n-1]}{8} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the $\frac{y[n-1]}{4}$ value is shifted to left two times and then subtracted to $y[n-1]$. In the same way, $\frac{x[n]}{8}$ and $\frac{x[n-1]}{8}$ are shifted to left three times and then these values are added. Finally, both results are added to obtain the filter output.

From Equation 1, we estimate the normalized frequency as follows:

$$x = e^{-2\pi F} \quad (3)$$

where $x = 0.75$ and the normalized frequency equal to 0.045 for both signals. Thus, the cut-off frequency is equal to 1.8 KHz for the sampling frequency of the macaque monkey signal ($F_s = 40$ KHz) and 450Hz for the human pancreatic signal ($F_s = 10$ KHz).

The next step is to create a high-pass filter, to do this we use spectral inversion from low-pass and all-pass filters, where the latest could be the original signal (See [16] for more details).

2.3 Action Potential Detection

Due to the nature and complexity of our bio-signals, an adaptive threshold was performed to detect action potentials. Thus, the threshold is real-time adapted to the new sample before the next one is read. To do this, we considered the method proposed in [5] for an adaptive threshold, where the detection is automatic and the threshold is adapted to stay above the background noise level of the signal. Thereby, at each time an Action Potential is above the threshold, a logical true signal is emitted and vice-versa. The main idea is to set a threshold low enough to detect Action Potentials and high enough to discard peaks from the background noise.

The adaptive threshold is based on the measure of the gaussian noise of a bio-signal during its acquisition. It is known that biological noise, tends to have a gaussian distribution, therefore, when we use a high-pass filter the mean value of the bio-signal has a mean of zero. Thereby, any DC offset has been removed and the noise is equivalent to its Root Mean Square (RMS) value, which is the standard deviation σ of our bio-signal [5]. This hypothesis relies on one feature of a gaussian distribution, where the probability density function of a random variable in a gaussian distribution is given by its mean μ and standard deviation σ .

The probability of the random variable for an event above the $\mu + \sigma$ is 15.9 %. This hypothesis is also applied when the signal has N samples, i.e. the gaussian distribution for the 15.9 % of these samples will be above $\mu + \sigma$. Consequently, the noise is equivalent to the standard deviation σ , due that the mean μ is equal to zero [15].

In Figure 2, it can be appreciated that the threshold estimation is similar to a proportional controller, where the standard deviation (σ) is calculated with the

Fig. 2: Circuit diagram of the standard deviation approximation and action potential detection. Illustration inspired from [5].

hypothesis that only the 15.9 % of the samples will be above its value. Also, we can observe a low-pass filter which computes the mean proportion of the sample above σ . Consequently, this mean proportion is compared with the reference of 15.9 % before mentioned. Finally, the loop is completed by including a constant K , that corrects the standard deviation (σ) approximation value to be compared with the bio-signal. In order to accentuate the detection of the action potentials, we amplified the approximation of σ by a constant value N , where a bigger value represents a lower probability of the noise to be above this value. Therefore, action potentials are detected and the probability of the noise to pass the $N\sigma$ value is lower.

2.4 Detection of action potentials from macaque monkey and pancreatic human bio-signals

In Figure 3, most common action potentials shapes found in the macaque monkey and the human pancreatic bio-signals are shown. These shapes are commonly originated in one or more cells depending on the recording conditions. From such figure, we can clearly appreciate the two phases of the action potential in the macaque monkey signal, contrary to those in the human pancreatic signal where the negative phase is smaller to the positive one.

To perform the detection of macaque monkey action potentials we used two thresholds, in that way the true detection of action potentials has a lower uncertainty against false negative and positive detections. Subsequently, we will always detect negative phases and afterwards positive phases. This is shown in Figure 4, where both phases are detected for the adaptive threshold, and both detectors generate a true pulse with the same width of the peak when it is above or under the adaptive threshold.

For the detection of action potentials in human pancreatic signals, it could be better the use of only the positive threshold. This is mainly due that in the negative phase the hyperpolarization could make the noise affect the detection, such as

Fig. 3: Action potentials shapes of macaque monkey and human pancreatic bio-signals.

Fig. 4: Macaque monkey action potential detected in both phases, positive and negative.

in Figure 5. Here, the hyperpolarization is not low enough and the detector could produces two pulses, due to the background noise in the bio-signal.

Fig. 5: Human pancreatic Action Potential detected for both detector positive and detector negative.

2.5 Mean action potential

The Mean Action Potential is computed as the average of the sample shapes of each Action Potential detected when these pass through a low pass filter. This can be observed in a step response of a low-pass filter, where the low-pass filter

output reaches the step value after certain samples. The use of a low-pass filter is approximated to the well known average value for certain amount of data as shown in Equation 4. In our case, we have to average each sample of the detected Action Potential in order to save the whole Action Potential shape.

$$M[n] = \sum_{i=1}^D \frac{S_i[n]}{D} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 6: General diagram for computing the Mean Action Potential shape by using a low-pass filter equation. The last output shape $L_i[n - 1]$, present shape $S_i[n]$, and last shape detected $S_i[n - 1]$ are stored to compute the new mean shape.

In Figure 6, L is the output of the filter, i is the index of the 32 possible samples of the Action Potential shape (Monkey Action Potential), S represents the detected Action potentials. To compute the Mean Action Potential shape, the last shape computed for the filter is needed and stored, as well as the present detection and last detection shape.

The use of a low-pass filter is better in terms of memory resources than the average. The comparative results of both shapes by using a low-pass filter and the common average equation is shown in Figure 7, where it can be observed that the approximation gives good results.

2.6 Correlation

The correlation is commonly described as a measure to compare two signals. If our signals are similar a positive correlation result is expected. In that way, we use correlation to compare the actual Action Potential detected, with the Mean Action Potential shape that is computed by using a low-pass filter. Then, the correlation is enable to determinate the measure between the two Action Potentials shapes, each time and Action Potential is detected. Thereby, having a measure where we can know if the Action Potential detected is similar in shape to the Mean Action Potential shape by observing the correlation shape generated. The common equation of correlation is presented in 5.

Fig. 7: Compute and comparative of average and low-pass filter approximation for computing the Mean Action Potential shape using 101 detections.

$$Corr_{x,y} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] y[n] \quad (5)$$

Here, $y[n]$ has a specific length N and it is the known shape, while $x[n]$ is a shifted signal whose elements change with each iteration, new samples are taken and a new correlation value is computed. Therefore, if we correlate all the samples of both detected Action Potential shapes, a positive value will be presented when both signals $x[n]$ and $y[n]$ match [16].

2.7 Correlation Patterns

The correlation shape is the expected result with a positive value when both shapes match. Nevertheless, two negatives values are generated, it is the result of both phases (negative and positive) being correlated, the negative value tell us that while one phase increases the other one decreases. This is the result of both phases being correlated when the signals are shifted [16].

We observed in both bio-signals, macaque monkey and human pancreatic that six possible patterns could be easily detected, by using the same technique of two adaptive thresholds as in Figure 4, but now we applied this to detect Correlation Patterns and their phases, such as the positive that tell us that an Action Potential is similar to the Mean Action Potential computed, and the negative ones, when both phases exist in the detected Action Potential. The six patterns observed are illustrated in Figure 8.

2.7.1 Data storage and numerical results

The Action Potentials were stored in four possible cases:

Fig. 8: Correlation patterns to be classified and detected.

- When both negative and positive detectors were triggered.
- When only the positive detector was triggered.
- When only the negative detector was triggered.
- When only the positive detector was triggered between the refractory period.

The correlation patterns were classified only using the detections when both negative and positive detectors were triggered and separated in six possible patterns. In the next section, we will show the numerical results and how the detections when both negative and positive detectors were triggered and classified in different groups. Depending on the detected correlation pattern, we have results for the monkey macaque signal in Figure 9 and for the human pancreatic in Figure 10.

3 Hardware Architecture Design

In this work, two main architectures were designed. The first one for the macaque monkey biosignal, and the second one for the human pancreatic biosignal. These two architectures were named as *Monkey_module* and *Pancreatic_module*. The only difference between the architectures is that in the pancreatic module we detect positive Action Potentials and two-phases Action Potentials that have positive and

Fig. 9: Macaque Monkey Action Potentials detected and classified by Correlation Pattern.

negative phases, as well as the False positives and False negatives. Therefore, we used one more FIFO memory.

The general hardware architecture for the two designs is shown in Figure 11. The architecture designs were built with several sub-modules and a global FSM that controls and coordinates the Action Potential detection and classification. The generic inputs of this module are explained as follows:

- ***Input.Frequency***. It is the frequency at which we provide new samples in the the *Sdcard_readstream* module. This input goes to the *periodic_timer* module and produces a pulse that indicates to the *Sdcard_readstream* module when has to give a new sample. This input value has to be in hertz.
- ***N.Threshold***. It is the adjustment value for the positive and negative thresholds. The higher value corresponds to the positive threshold and the lower to the negative threshold. The range of this adjustment is an integer from 0 to 15. The changes of the thresholds can be seen in the Pmod OLEDrgb display when *Switch_3* input is 0. These thresholds are used to detect the Action Potentials.

(a) Human Pancreatic Action Potentials detected.

(b) APs classified in Pattern 0

(c) APs classified in Pattern 2

(d) APs classified in Pattern 3

(e) APs classified in Pattern 4

(f) APs classified in Pattern 5

Fig. 10: Human Pancreatic Action Potentials detected and classified by Correlation Pattern.

- ***K_Adjustment***. It is the adjustment of the standard deviation computed to be compared with the band-pass filter output. The range of this input goes from 0 to 16383. Although, we recommend the use of values such as 10,100,1000,1000. To compute the standard deviation we set this value in 1000 for a better performance with both signals.
- ***N_Threshold_C***. It is the adjustment value for the positive and negative correlation thresholds, The higher value corresponds to the positive threshold and

Fig. 11: General hardware architecture for the two designs.

the lower to the negative threshold. The range of this adjustment is an integer from 0 to 15. The changes of the thresholds can be seen in the Pmod OLE-Drbg display when *Switch_3* input is 1. These thresholds are used to detect the Correlation Patterns.

- ***K_Adjustment_C***. It is the adjustment of the standard deviation computed to be compared with the Correlation signal output. The range of these inputs goes from 0 to 16383. Although, we recommend the use of values such as 10,100,1000,1000. To compute the standard deviation we set this value in 100 for a better performance with both signals.
- ***FIFO_DEPTH***. It is the deep of the FIFO memories or memory locations available in each FIFO memory.
- ***FIFO_WORD_SIZE***. It is the size length of the detection samples saved in the FIFO memories. The default value is 32-bit.
- ***RAMS_DEPTH***. It is the deep of the RAM memories or memory locations available in each RAM memory. These memories are used to compute the Mean Action Potential shape. This value is the exponent number of a power of two. That means (2^R *RAMS_DEPTH*).
- ***RAMS_WORD_SIZE***. It is the size length of the samples saved in the RAM memories. The default value is 16-bit, which is the same length of the samples coming from the SD card.
- ***START_TEST_IN***. Here, this is an integer value in the range of 0 to 4095. The number input is the sample number at which detection and classification processes are enabled.
- ***FINISH_TEST_IN***. This input determines when the detection and classification processes end. When this happens the module will stop all the process.

The Global FSM for the control of the whole process is presented in Figure 12. The main states are explained as follows:

- ***Waiting***. This state waits for the *timer_strobe* signal coming from the periodic timer module and the *Authorized* signal coming from the FSM. It controls the UART communication and the *next_sd_data* state moves to the next transition when both signals are set to high.
- ***next_sd_data***. This state indicates by the *read_sample* output to the *Sd-card_readstream* module when a new sample needs to be read. Consequently, the FSM passes to next transition the *waiting_SD* state until the *data_ready* input stays on high. Then, the new sample is ready to be read from the *data_out* port output of the *Sdcard_readstream* module.
- ***passing_Low***. This state enable the *IIR filter* module by the *read_sample* output for computing a new filtered value when the data is ready in the *data_out* port output from the *Sdcard_readstream* module. Consequently, the FSM passes to the next *waiting_Low* state where the filter module is waited until the *ready_IIR* input is set to high. Then the high-pass filter value is ready too.
- ***passing_Low***. This state enables the second IIR filter module for computing the value in the *Band-pass* filter when the *read_sample_Band* output is set to high. Therefore, the FSM passes to the next transition the *waiting_Band* state where the module is waited until the *ready_Band_IIR* input is set to high by the Band-pass filter module indicating that the filtered value is ready to be read.

- **Detection.** The state enables the compute of a new Threshold value when *read_detection* output is set to high. This new Threshold value computed is used to be compared with the Band-pass filtered value for detecting Action Potentials. In addition, when the *read_detection* output is triggered also the Correlation compute is enabled, and after the FSM passes to the *waiting_Corre_Compute* until the *ready_Corre_Compute* input is set to high, it indicates that the Correlation value is ready to be read for the *Top_Level.Threshold.Correlation* module and passing to the next transition the *start_Corre_threshold* state where new Correlation threshold value is computed in the *Detection_and_Classification* module when the FSM passes by the *waiting_Corre_Detection* state, hereby waiting for the Correlation threshold compute which is ready when the *ready_Corre_Threshold* input is set high.
- **Plots.** This state has two possible transitions depending on the *Disable* input value, which comes from the switch inputs in the FPGA board. The first transition is when this input is low, in this case the FSM machine does not wait for the *Pmod_OLEDrgb* module to properly plot the signals, so the system is running emulating a real-time acquisition processing each sample read thought the frequency which is proportionate by the *periodic_timer* module. The second transition is when the *waiting_OLED* state is reached, that is when the *Disable* input is set high. Consequently, the FSM waits until all the samples have sent to the input into the *Pmod_OLEDrgb* module, therefore it waits for the *Shift_done* input, when this is set high indicates that the samples in the display have been properly shifted .

3.1 IIR filter module

This module is based on Equation 2 where the raw data saved in the SD card is low-pass filtered. The IIR filter has an internal 16.3 fixed-point precision, where 16-bit are for the integer part and 3-bit are for the decimal part, and the filter's output only gives the 16-bit integer part. The module is shown in Figure 13. Here, the *Sample* input receives the data coming from the output *data_out* of the *SDcard_readstream* module. Then, the *new_sample* input is set to high when a new sample is ready to be filtered. Consequently, the *IIR_ready* output is set to low while the process finish and the computed value is put on the *IIR_output*.

The FSM that controls the low-pass filter output is shown in Figure 14. The main states are explained as follows:

- **waiting.** This state passes to the next transition, the *saving_past* state, until the *new_sample* input is set high, indicating that a new sample is ready to be processed.
- **saving_past.** This state loads the last filtered output and the last sample input in both registers, *Register_Yn-1* and *Register_Xn-1* and then pass to the next *saving_new_sample* state.
- **saving_new_sample.** Here, the new sample is loaded in the *Register_Xn* and in the next clock cycle the FSM pass to the next transition the *saving_Result* state.
- **saving_Result .** In this state the computed filtered data is loaded in *Register_Result* and the new value is ready and put on the *IIR_output* . Finally,

Fig. 12: Global FSM that controls all the process in the architecture.

the FSM reaches one more time the *waiting* state triggering the *IIR_ready* and the output indicates that the module is ready to compute a new value.

Fig. 13: IIR filter module

Fig. 14: FSM to compute the IIR low-pass filter output.

3.2 Top level threshold module

This module is based on the diagram presented in Figure 2, where the σ approximation is computed, the fixed point for the standard deviation value is 17.14, where only 16-bit of the integer part are taken in adjustment K part to be compared with the 16-bit IIR band-pass filter input. By the way, for the Threshold value it has a fixed point of 22.14, and the same way 16-bit are taken for the integer part in adjustment N. The main parts of this diagram are implemented in this module, a comparator between the σ approximation and the output of the band-pass filter. A low-pass filter is needed to compute the mean value of the sam-

ples that have been above the threshold. A subtractor to make the operation with the theory 15.9 % . After, two multipliers are needed, one for the K factor, and the other one for the N factor. The negative threshold computes only the second complement of the $(N\sigma)$ value.

Fig. 15: Top level Threshold module.

This module can be configured with both N and K factors in the *N_Threshold* and *K_Adjustment* generic inputs respectively. As the passed modules, the *new_sample* module input is set high for one clock cycle and at the same time the band-pass filter output is put in the *Band_pass_value* module input. Then, a new threshold value is computed and when the value is ready the *Detection_ready* output is set high. The new threshold value is put on *Threshold_P* output for the positive threshold, and on *Threshold_N* output for the negative threshold value. Finally, if during that cycle the *Band_pass_value* is higher than *Threshold_P* value, the *Detection_P* output will be put in high. On the contrary, if the *Band_pass_value* is lower than *Threshold_N* value, the *Detection_N* will be put it high. These outputs are ready when the *Detection_ready* output module is set high and is held it on and the threshold value is put on both the *Threshold_P* and *Threshold_N* module outputs with size of 16-bit, the same size of the band-pass filter output which need to be compared.

The FSM that controls the compute of the adaptive threshold value is show in Figure 16. The main states of this FSM are explained as follows:

- *waiting*. This state waits for the *new_sample* input in the module for starting to compute a new threshold value each time a new sample was read from the SD card module. The next transition is the *enable_filter* state.

Fig. 16: FSM for computing the Threshold value.

- *enable_filter*. This state enables the process in the *Top_IIR_Threshold* by the *En_filter* signal for computing the mean value of the samples that have been above the (σ) approximation value. When the value is ready the *IIR_ready* module output is set high and the FSM passes to the next transition the *waiting_filter* state.
- *waiting_filter*. This state waits until the *IIR_ready* module output is set high, indicating that the module has finished to compute the new value, and the FSM passes to the next transition the *saving_factor* state.
- *saving_factor*. This module load the value after the Factor k multiplier which comes from the 0.159 subtraction by the *LD_Reg_Factor_1* signal. Consequently, the FSM passes to the *saving_Result* state.
- *saving_Result*. In this *saving_Result* state the adaptive threshold value is loaded in *Register_Threshold* register by the *LD_Threshold* signal. Then, the Threshold values compute are set on the *Threshold_P* and *Threshold_N* module outputs, as well as the module outputs of the comparators are put on *Detection_P* and *Detection_N* module outputs. Finally, the FSM returns to the *waiting* state triggering the *Detection_ready* output, indicating that the module has finished the compute.

3.3 Detection and Classification module

This module is the most extensive one designed in the hardware architecture, due to many FSM are needed for saving the maximum and minimum values, for saving the Action Potential shapes detected in the RAM memories, to compute the Mean Action Potential shape, in order to compute the correlation signal, for detecting the Action Potentials, to detect the Correlation Patterns and save and classifier the Action Potential detections. The principal module is shown in the Figure 17.

The main parts that contains this module are as follows:

- Saving maximum and minimum

Fig. 17: Pricipal module for saving and sorting Action Potentials

- Action Potential Detection
- Action Potential Save Order
- Action Potential Saved in RAM
- Mean Action Potential Shape Compute
- Correlation Compute
- Correlation Thresholds
- Correlation Pattern Detection

In the *Saving maximum and minimum* part, we show how the maximum and minimum values are found. The detection of Action Potentials, as well as the detection of False Positives and False Negatives is shown in *Action Potential Detection*. The *Action Potential Save Order* part is dedicated to create a signal that order to the *Action Potential Saved in RAM* saves the samples saved in the *register_window* backup samples. The *Mean Action Potential Shape Compute* describes the compute of the Mean Action Potential, it started when the Action Potential shape detected has been saved in present spike RAM. The *Correlation Compute* parts show how the correlation signals is computed with the *register_window* samples and the Mean Action Potential shape saved in the Mean spike RAM. The *Correlation Thresholds* part is based on the module aforementioned in Figure 15 and carry out the same task over the correlation signal for computing the adaptive threshold above the background noise level. The *Correlation Pattern Detection* detects the correlation patterns aforementioned in Figure 8. Finally, the system results, such as the detection numbers and FIFO outputs, are displayed by the *7-segment display* part.

3.4 UART modules

The purpose of these two sub-modules is to communicate the FPGA by a UART controller to start, stop and pause the intern process in the *Topmodel* module. Here, the data is sent by the keyboard in the common communication protocol RS-232. The data transfer rate is 115200 kbps. When the UART receiver module validates the data in the UART line, the *dat_en* output is set to high for one clock cycle and the chart data is ready in the *dat* module output.

After, the UART sender module, receives the pulse generated from the UART receiver module by the *dat_en* module input, and the chart data in the *dat* module input is sent to be display in the terminal. In our case we use the ASCII values *01100001* (a) to start the process, *01100010* (b) to stop and *01100011* (c) for reading only one sample at the time.

- *stopped*. When the FSM stays in this state, the *Authorized* output is set low, then the whole system is stopped, such as the detection and classification process which are enabled by the FSM. The possible transitions are the *running* or *single* states. The *running* state is reached if the *data_en_from_UART* input is set to high and the character sent in the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *a* character. Similarly, the *single* state is reached if the *data_en_from_UART* input is set to high and the character sent in the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *c* character.

- *running*. As aforementioned this state is reached when the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *a* character. The transition to the *stopped* state is reached in four possible ways. The first one when the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *b* character. The second one is when the *Disible* input value is *01* or *10* and the *Detected* input signal is high triggered, indicating that a Detection has been detected by the system, such as an Action Potential, False Positive or False Negative. Finally, the fourth one when the *read.Finished* input is set to high when the sample counter reach to the sample number entered by the generic *FINISH_TEST_IN* input in the *Toplevel* module. In addition, the *single* also is reached when the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *c* character and the *data_en_from_UART* input signal is set high indicating that a new character value has been typed in the keyword. Besides, when the FSM stays in this state, the *Authorized* output is set high by indicating that the samples have to be processed for the different modules.
- *single*. As aforementioned this state is reached when the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *c* character. Also, such as the passed states both the *stopped* and the *running* states are reached. The *stopped* state is reached after a sample is read from the SD card module which is indicated by the *timer_strobe* input signal which comes from the *periodic_timer* module, in that way, only one sample is read at the time. In addition also it is reached when the *b* character is sent by the *data_from_UART* and when the *data_en_from_UART* input signal is set high. Finally the as it been described the *running* state is reached if the *data_en_from_UART* input is set to high and the character sent in the *data_from_UART* input signal is the *a* character. Besides, when the FSM stays in this state, the *Authorized* output is set high by indicating that the samples have to be processed for the different modules.

3.5 Periodic timer module

This module proportionates a pulse frequency of the value entered in the *TIMER_FREQU_HZ* module input in Hz. This pulse is taken into account to proportionate the saved samples in the SD card by the *Sdcard_readstream* module. The module is shown in Figure 18.

The generic input *TIMER_FREQU_HZ* determinate the pulse frequency in the *timer_tick* output, while the generic *CLK_FREQU_HZ* input is the clock frequency of the FPGA. The *pause* input pauses the generation of the pulse in the *timer_tick* output.

3.6 SD card module

The SD card modules are *SDcard_raw_access_v2* and *SDcard_readstream*, (documentation of these modules could be found in Teaching resources - Y. Bornat-SDcard). These modules make possible to transfer data between the local buffers in the FPGA and the SD card. Reading data for the buffers is similar to RAM access, the data can be 8, 16, 32 and 64 bits wide. In our case, we used a 16-bit data word size. The module *SDcard_readstream* module is shown in Figure 19.

Fig. 18: Periodic timer module. author's module: Yannick Bornat

Fig. 19: SDcard_readstream for reading bio-signal samples from SD card in slot in Nexys 4 FPGA. Illustration from Teaching resources - Y. Bornat

The use of these modules is straightforward, only the *Main SDcard interface* signals have to be connected properly in the file with extension *.ucf*. For reading new samples from the output *data_out*, the *data_read* input have to be set high for a clock cycle and return to low. After, *data_empty_n* is set low and when the data is ready to be read in *data_out* the *data_empty_n* signal will be set high one more time and then the process can be repeated. The system clock frequency for the module is 100 MHz.

3.7 Pmod OLED module

The use of a display in a FPGA is helpful, in our case, we use a 96 x 64 pixel RGB OLED Display with 16-bit color resolution (Diligent link). The display can plot

signals, pictures and more, through a standard SPI interface. The Pmod OLEDrgb used is shown in Figure 20.

Fig. 20: Pmod OLEDrgb features a 96 x 64 pixel RGB OLED display that is capable of 16-bit color resolution.. Illustration from Diligent

For plotting the signals in the Pmod OLEDrgb, we used a module which its documentation can be found in Teaching resources - Y. Bornat- Pmod OLEDrgb, this module is able to plot four signals up in the OLED screen, the four signals that we showed in the OLED display were the band-pass filter output to observe the Action Potentials, the Correlation signal to observe the Correlation Patterns and the positive and negative thresholds. The *PmodOLEDrgb_sigplot* module which controls the signal plotting and shifting is presented in Figure 21.

Fig. 21: SDCard_readstream for reading bio-signal samples from SD card in slot in Nexys 4 FPGA. Illustration from Teaching resources - Y. Bornat

Fig. 22: Pmod OLEDrgb display. Filtered signal (Action Potential) green, Correlation Pattern yellow, Threshold positive cyan, Threshold negative purple.

Figure 22, shows the signals plotted in the Pmod OLEDrgb display. The Band-pass filter output is the green plot where we can observe an Macaque monkey Action Potential. The yellow one is the Correlation signal computed where we can appreciate the Correlation Pattern generated to classify this Action Potential detected. The cyan one is the Positive Threshold computed, this could be the detection positive threshold or the correlation positive threshold depending on the *Switch_3* input. In the same way, the detection negative threshold is plotted in the purple plot, where depending on the *Switch_3* input, the detection negative threshold or the correlation negative threshold are plotted.

4 Results

4.1 FPGA Monkey hardware architecture results

The presented hardware architecture was implemented using the XILINX ISE WebPACK and it was synthesized for the Nexys 4 board. This board is based on the Artix-7 FPGA family. The module uses 2,083 slice registers, 2,915 LUTs, and can operate at a maximum frequency of 104.965 MHz. In Table 1, we present a summary of the logical resource consumption for the hardware architecture.

Table 1: Summary of the logical resource consumption for the Monkey hardware architecture. It was synthesized for the XC7A100T-1CSG324C FPGA device.

Resource	Consumption
slice registers	2,083 (1%)
LUTs	2,915 (4%)
Maximum operation frequency	104.965 MHz

In Figure 23, we can observe when an Action Potential is detected in the FPGA showing the band-pass filter signal, the correlation signal and the threshold.

Fig. 23: Monkey_module detecting a two-phases Action Potential (green), Correlation Pattern (yellow) and positive and negative threshold values. 7-segment displays showing the actual number of two-phases Action Potentials detected

In this module, the Generic inputs for properly run the detection and classification processes are shown in Table 2. The $K_Adjustment$ and $K_Adjustment_C$ input values were tested in the FPGA architecture showing a good performance when computing the detection and correlation thresholds being less sensitive to the presence of Macaque monkey Action Potentials and Correlation Patterns. These thresholds were put above the background noise on the biosignal and on the correlation signal computed internally. This was proved by using the Pmod OLEDrgb display and shown in Figure 23.

Table 2: Generic parameters used in Monkey_module

Generic input	Input value
Input_Frequency	40000
N_Threshold	[0,...,15]
K_Adjustment	1000
N_Threshold_C	10
K_Adjustment_C	100
FIFO_DEPTH	4
FIFO_WORD_SIZE	32
RAMS_DEPTH	5
RAMS_WORD_SIZE	16
START_TEST_IN	2500
FINISH_TEST_IN	9411000

The detection results by using this Monkey_module are shown in Table 3. The results of each Threshold value is shown in this table. Here, the Action Potentials that triggered both detector are shown in the two-phases columns, as well as the False positives and False negatives detected in their respective columns. For False Negatives or Falses positives are those detections that did not have a second phases detection between the Action Potential period. These values were extracted from the FPGA by using the 7-segment display.

Table 3: FPGA results. Two-phases Action Potentials, False positives, False Negatives for Macaque monkey biosignal

Threshold value	Two-phases	False positives	False negatives
5	2055	5470	15071
7	1228	931	5902
9	1037	225	2817
11	979	68	1402
13	952	19	689
15	921	10	395

Table 4, shows where each two-phases Action Potential were classified or sorted out. This is depending on the Correlation Pattern detected after its detection. The possible patterns are six, as it is shown in the table. All the Correlation patterns were detected using a Correlation threshold value of 10.

Table 4: FPGA results. Two-phases Action Potentials classified by Correlation Pattern for Macaque monkey biosignal

Threshold value	Pat 0	Pat 1	Pat 2	Pat 3	Pat 4	Pat 5	Total detections
5	680	3	331	178	766	97	2055
7	99	2	94	121	868	44	2053
9	30	0	24	53	912	18	1037
11	9	0	8	26	923	13	979

Table 4: FPGA results. Two-phases Action Potentials classified by Correlation Pattern for Macaque monkey biosignal

Threshold value	Pat 0	Pat 1	Pat 2	Pat 3	Pat 4	Pat 5	Total detections
13	7	0	0	18	916	11	952
15	5	0	0	12	896	8	921

4.2 FPGA Human Pancreatic hardware architecture results

The hardware architecture for the Human pancreatic biosignal was designed using the ISE WebPACK of XILINX on a NEXYS 4 Artix-7 FPGA. The module uses 3,645 slice registers, 3,985 LUTs, and can operate at a maximum frequency of 100.654 MHz. (Figure 24, shows when an Action Potential is detected in the FPGA showing the band-pass filter signal, the Correlation signal and the threshold for detecting Action Potentials or the Correlation Patterns generated. Table 5 presents a summary of the logical resource consumption for the hardware architecture.

Table 5: Summary of the logical resource consumption for the Human Pancreatic hardware architecture. It was synthesized for the XC7A100T-1CSG324C FPGA device.

Resource	Consumption
slice registers	3,645 (4%)
LUTs	3,985 (7%)
Maximum operation frequency	100.654 MHz

(a) Pmod OLEDrgb display showing a Human pancreatic Action Potential detected by its thresholds

(b) Pmod OLEDrgb display showing a Correlation Pattern generated after detected a Human pancreatic Action Potential detected

Fig. 24: Pancreatic_module detecting a two-phases Action Potential (green), Correlation Pattern (yellow) and positive and negative threshold values

In this module the Generic inputs for properly run the detection and classification processes are shown in Table 6. The *K_Adjustment* and *K_Adjustment_C* input values were tested in the FPGA architecture showing a good performance when computing the detection and correlation thresholds being less sensitive to the presence of Human pancreatic Action Potentials and Correlation Patterns. By the way these values are the same that in the Monkey_module. These thresholds were put above the background noise on the biosignal and on the Correlation signal computed internally. This was proved by using the Pmod OLEDrgb display as it is shown in Figure 24.

Table 6: Generic parameters used in Pancreatic_module

Generic input	Input value
Input_Frequency	10000
N_Threshold	[0,...,15]
K_Adjustment	1000
N_Threshold_C	10
K_Adjustment_C	100
FIFO_DEPTH	4
FIFO_WORD_SIZE	32
RAMS_DEPTH	7
RAMS_WORD_SIZE	16
START_TEST_IN	750
FINISH_TEST_IN	130000

The detections result by using this Pancreatic_module are shown in Table 7. The results of each Threshold value is shown in this table. Here, the Action Potentials that triggered both detector are shown in the two-phases columns, as well as the False positives and False negatives detected in their respective columns and in addition we added an extra detection for those detections that only had a positive trigger event between an Action Potential period. For False Negatives are those detections that did not have a second phases detection between the Action Potential period. For False positives are those that stayed above the threshold for more than an Action Potential period. These values were extracted from the FPGA by using the 7-segment display.

Table 7: FPGA results. Two-phases Action Potentials, False positives, False Negatives for Human pancreatic biosignal

Threshold value	Two-phases	Positive	False positive	False negative
2	415	128	2	518
3	92	192	1	202
4	48	30	0	17
5	24	35	0	2
6	5	51	0	0

Table 8, shows where each two-phases Action Potential were classified or sorted out. This is depending on the Correlation Pattern detected after its detection. The possible patterns are six, as it is shown in the table. All the Correlation patterns were detected using a Correlation threshold value of 10.

Table 8: FPGA results. Two-phases Action Potentials classified by Correlation Pattern for Human pancreatic biosignal

Threshold value	Pat 0	Pat 1	Pat 2	Pat 3	Pat 4	Pat 5	Total detections
2	394	1	13	0	2	5	415

Table 8: FPGA results. Two-phases Action Potentials classified by Correlation Pattern for Human pancreatic biosignal

Threshold value	Pat 0	Pat 1	Pat 2	Pat 3	Pat 4	Pat 5	Total detections
3	47	1	22	9	4	9	92
4	0	0	5	6	33	4	48
5	0	0	1	4	19	0	24
6	0	0	1	0	3	1	5

5 Conclusions

In this work we create two hardware modules, one dedicated to detection of Action Potentials in Macaque monkey signals and other one dedicated to Action Potentials from Human pancreatic biosignals. Both modules save the sample number where each two-phases Action Potential was detected, which is the maximum value found in the Action Potential shape. This was performed by the adaptive threshold presented in [5], which follows the hypothesis that the background noise will overtake its standard deviation value with 15% of the samples. This adaptive threshold presented good performance when good coefficients are selected, whose values were presented in Table 2 and Table 6 for hardware. The use of FIFO memories in the modules was thinking about the connection to other devices that probably works at a lower clock frequency, with the use of FIFO memories we guaranty that the detection data is not loosed.

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